

CHOREOGRAPHY IN THE COLLECTIVE PRACTICE OF DANCE-DRAMAS OF RUKMINI DEVI

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Abstract:

Rukmini Devi was a key figure in the revival of Indian dance in the early independence era. Her innovations pertain to both solo and dance-drama forms. The paper deals with analysis of two important scenes of her Ramayana production- *Sabari moksham* which show her choreographic strategies and reflect her style with regard to dance drama and shows how she worked with aesthetic consciousness of her times during the nationalist struggle of the 1930s and 40s. Analysis has used terminology as in Abhinayadarpana which is used as the textual reference for Bharatanatyam. It finds how dimensions with regard to stage aesthetics, costuming of characters, intonation of sollu, character and context-oriented use of nritta and angika abhinaya broadened the scope of collective performance in her works.

Key words: Bharatanatyam, Rukmini Devi, Dance-drama, Choreography, Movement analysis, Nationalism, collective belonging

Introduction

Rukmini Devi, inspired by Anna Pavlova when she witnessed her performance in 1924, started learning Bharatanatyam in 1932, initially from Gowri ammal, a devadasi at the Kapaleeshwarar temple at Chennai and later from other traditional nattuvanars at her newly established centre at Adyar. Her contribution to

the revival of the solo form of Bharatanatyam and the changes she made to the form have been critically viewed in the post-colonial discourse (Allen, 1997; Chakravorty, 1998; OShea, 1998; Meduri, 1988; Coorlawala, 2004; Puthenedam, 2014). She has also been hailed as revivalist and transnationalist who gave succour to the nattuvanars and Carnatic music composers at her institution- Kalakshetra (Meduri, 2004; Natarajan, 1997; Khokar, 2013). Studies on her dance-dramas have not been researchers' area of focus perhaps because it has been considered as inspired reworkings of Bhagavathamela nataka or Kuravanji. This paper undertakes movement analysis to show how Rukmini Devi worked with aesthetic consciousness of her times. The scenes show choreographic liberty which she exercises with regard to body movements, costumes, jewellery, vachika and movement patterns across stage in view of adapting elements of Bharatanatyam, a typically solo form to a collective form to be performed on the proscenium stage. The main objectives of this research are to understand significant features of choreographic strategies employed in the introduction scenes of Jatayu and Surpanakha through movement analysis. It also locates and contextualises her dance-dramas within the context of nationalism creating cultural consciousness, collective belonging and pan-India vision

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Nationalism, Collective belonging and Dance-drama

At the turn of the last century when dance in the west started awakening to a new modern era and stories from the orient were seen with awe, ballet dancers Ruth St Denis, Ted Shawn and Anna Pavlova danced to themes inspired from India. This in turn kindled the verve to revitalize our indigenous dance forms by dancers like Uday Shankar and later, Rukmini Devi. A collective national consciousness fed by the oriental vision of an India with glorious past led to revival of arts and with it, the establishment of institutions like Vallathol's Kalamandalam, Tagore's Shantiniketan, Rukmini Devi's Kalakshetra, Uday Shankar's centre at Almora and many others that followed. A sense of collective belonging during the united struggle for Indian independence in the 1920s and 30s also created a platform to explore innovative ways of presenting traditional dance forms. Partner dances, dance ballets, and dance-dramas which were done by two or more persons gained popularity at a time when languishing and little-known solo regional dance forms had just begun to see limelight and be taught in the above institutions. Notable among them were partner dances of Pavlova and Uday Shankar, Gopinath and Ragini Devi, Louise lightfoot and Ananda Shivaraman. Dance-dramas written by Tagore, dance ballets created by Uday Shankar and Rukmini Devi were composed to involve collective dancing. Alongside, folklore, ballads, legends were being revived in a bid to promote cultural consciousness and garner support for the making of nationalist identity. An example can be found in harikatha, an art of story-telling with music, drama, dance and philosophy based on narrations from puranas. It became a popular art form during the pre-independence period that it found mention

even in literary novels like Raja Rao's *Kanthapura*. The new orientalism during this period was built around an episteme created a century earlier, with parameters of textual authenticity to make tradition look 'authentic'. Oriental leanings coupled with nationalistic fervor worked towards bringing a pan-Indian emphasis essentializing upon and linking of the local with the national both in cultural and political spheres. An analogous case in point is Raja Ravi Varma's *The Galaxy of musicians* (Painted in 1889 in the early years when nationalism was at its nascent stages) portraying women musicians from different parts of India representing their culture through different musical instruments and traditional costumes but seated together and united in music. It represented the overarching slogan of Indian nationalism- 'Unity in diversity' and reflected the idea of collective nationalism. The idea of tradition as being embodied in ancient dance texts that were considered the new normative led to a linear reading of history with efforts to create a pan-Indian tradition of Indian dances as having had originated or had references from Bharata's *Natyashastra*. Thus, nationalistic ideals affected by orientalist leanings coupled with growing sense of collective belonging evoked a cultural consciousness that propagated nationalism with pan-Indian vision.

Concepts and Choreography

Rukmini Devi's thoughts on her dance-dramas were in consonance with the nationalist revivalists of her times. The 'spirituality' through dance infused into and propagated through her solo performances was continued in her dance-dramas too. She supposedly vouched for these works to be "a novel way of bringing religion to people", as "one of the ways to educate people to

understand divinity and express reverence” (1,2). Rukmini Devi’s early plays, those that she experimented with before and during her learning of Bharatanatyam, had themes that had close allegiance to the theosophical society’s ideology of which she was an ardent follower. Some of them were Hiawatha, The light of Asia, Bhishma, Kuchelavritam and Karaikal Ammaiyar. Sarada recounts that Rukmini Devi had played parts of swan, inspired from Pavlova’s famous episode of the dying swan, and the roles of Yasodhara, Ganga and Matsyagandhi and that the plays had theatrical actions, stage settings, dialogues, dance, tableau formations, chorus and instrumental music (3). Her first dance-drama was Kutrala Kuravanji produced in 1944 with support from Karaikkal Saradambal who was conversant with temple kuravanjis. In the Tamil county, Melattur bhagavatamela and Kuravanji natakam were some of the dance-drama forms that were still performed as rituals in temple premises during the early 1930s and 40s(4). Rukmini Devi’s dance-dramas totaling to twenty-five had adaptations of these including three kuravanjis and four bhagavatha mela natakams apart from her Ramayana series and others inspired from puranas and kavyas.

Sabari Moksham composed in 1965 is fourth in the Ramayana series amongst the twenty-five dance-dramas produced by Rukmini Devi. It is taken from Aranya Kandam, the third book of Valmiki’s Ramayana and deals with the abduction of Sita by Ravana. The music for the production is by Rajaram, the grandson of Mysore Vasudevacharya who composed music for the previous three in the series. Ramayana, considered to be the bedrock of Hindu morality, has portrayal of idealized characters and is presented with idealised Indian familial values. Rukmini Devi states how choreographing Ramayana has been

a unique experience for her. She says, “Rama and Sita belong to every Indian whatever be his station. We all feel proud of these divine figures whose divinity lies in their extreme humanity” (5). Jatayu sakhya and Surpanakha bhangam are the second and third episodes of Sabari Moksham which introduces two special characters in Ramayana- Jatayu and Surpanakha. Apart from these, the dance drama involves some very important incidents like Panchapsara sarovara, Maricha vadham, Sita apaharanam, Sitanveshanam, Jatayu -Ravana yudham and finally Sabari moksham (6). The two episodes chosen for analysis can be considered to involve some of the main features choreographic style that Rukmini Devi employs in her dance-drama creations. The references are from witnessing live performances of Sabhari Moksham as a student of Kalakshetra in the years 1997, 1998, 2000, and later at Rukmini Devi Birthday celebrations at Kalakshetra auditorium, Chennai, 2006

The paper looks at the choreographic strategies that she creates with these marginal characters that furthers the scope to develop many facets of the dance-drama. The episodes chosen for analysis here are not the ones with protagonists or mainstream characters like Rama, Sita or Ravana as the portrayal of these characters has larger possibility of replication of the solo format of techniques in presentation and thereby limiting the scope of exploring the choreographer’s contribution. The marginal characters that were developed through innovative choreography, presented new aesthetics perspectives to their portrayal in a drama and at the same time adapted and broadened the dimensions and scope of techniques of the solo form of Bharatanatyam when presented on a proscenium. Following is the interpretive analysis of different elements in the choreography of the two scenes

<p>Jatayu Patrapravesam A huge eagle is seen by Rama, Lakshmana and Sita. Suspecting the bird to be a rakshasa in disguise, Rama challenges it. The eagle introduces himself as Jatayu, son of Syeni and Aruna, and a friend of Rama's father Dasaratha(7).</p>	<p>Surpanakha Patrapravesanam After meeting Jatayu, Rama, Sita and Lakshmana proceed on their journey towards Panchavati. The next scene shows the entry of Surpanakha, sister of Ravana. Surpanakha's patrapravesham includes a description of Surpanakha set to Dhatuvardhani ragam in Misrachapu with interspersing theeramanams. Rukmini Devi is known to have compiled and composed the theeramanams.</p>
Literary references	
<p>Verse-Ragam: Amruthavarshini; Talam: Khanda Chapu "Tham neelajeemootha nikaashakalpam Supaançuroraskamudhaara veeryam Dadarsha tham patraratham prithivyaam Jataayusham shaantham ivaagnidhaavam" Trnsl: They saw Jatayu, who looked like rain-bearing dark clouds and with a white chest. He was very powerful but calm like a forest fire quenched (7).</p>	<p>Surpanakha enters to a jathi in fast tempo in Adi talam that goes like this: <i>Takkudu dikkudu dirrak kitta takkun taari tonkita nankita takkudu dikkudu dirrak kitta takkun taari tonkita nankita</i> <i>tonkita kitakita tonkita takatari kitataka takun tari kinajaga kinataka takkudikku thak kitatat tonga kitakita tadinginatom</i> .takku dikku tat tadinginatom, tat tadinginatom,tadinginatom A verse follows: <i>Saa thu shoorpanakha naama dashagreevasya rakshasaha: Bhagini rakshasi kachit aajagaama yadrychaya</i> <i>Vikrithaa cha viroopaa cha karaalaa nirnathodhari Viroopakshi sudryvrittaa daaruṇaa bhairavasvanaa</i> Following the jathis is the above verse that describes her as ugly fierce, with bulging belly, of mean character and hoarse voice.</p>
Stage setting and entry of character	
<p>Diffused light starts to fall in from the side wings; the character of Jatayu is at the centre of the stage. Gestures that help to identify Jatayu: stance-garuda mandala, hands-garuda hasta near chest; greeva and drishti following the jerky movements of the shira. The positioning of the anga, pratyanga and upanga together with the costume help us recognize general nature of the character Jatayu, when the dancer first appears on the stage itself.</p>	<p>The scene opens to the singing of the sollukattu "takkudu dikkudu...". Surpanakha enters from offstage behind the last wing. She moves towards upstage right end covering the entire stage in large gaits. As she does this, a blue light fades-in unevenly on the cyclorama. The cyclorama, along its entire and breadth, consists of a painting which is composed of hazy outlines of tree trunks, branches, vines, shrubs and their foliage. It is not densely picturised as the lighting fills the gaps with patches of darkness and ensures the creation of a perspective of thick and dense forest cover where the events happen. The rest is left to the imagination of the viewer. The prominence of blue, both on the background and on the stage floor, indicates that dusk has fallen. And with parts of stage or forest cover enveloped in darkness here and light there, it can be understood that moon is up above the horizon. The stage thus sets the ambience for the activities of Soorpanakha, a <i>nishaachari who</i>. is a nocturnal who actively roams about in the darkness of the night.in the dark forest. Surpanakha moves horizontally across in the first four avartanams of the jathi when a diffused red light from behind both the third right and left wings is projected on her upper body. The red lighting on Surpanakha's entry, though diffuse, falls sharply against silhouetting her profile, to reflect upon the nature of the character. It highlights at her entry itself, the fierceness of her facial features, the strong and sharp thumping moves made by her bulky self and the swift striking glances of her wandering look.</p>

Photo of both characters (Photo taken by the author)

Jatayu

Soorpanakha

Costume and Jewellery

A burnt sienna coloured attire suggestive of eagle's natural colour; material is of natural fabric that is rough textured with uneven edges extending towards the arms and underneath it with pleats and frills suggestive of its wings. A hood up till Garuda's temple acts as a head gear and with it, an extension covers the nose with an appendage indicative of the characteristic hooked beak of the bird.

The use of light weight ornaments made of knitted jute and the knee length kaccha (pyjama) provides ample scope for the artist to execute his movements with ease. The costume that conveniently fits in also marks the outline or silhouette of the four main parts of the bird's body vis-à-vis the head, wings, torso and the legs. This kind of fit attire heightens the effect of the adavus typical of Jatayu.

The colour red, as used in *katti vesham* of Kathakali, is used here too that is symbolic of her *tamasic* nature. Surpanakha is dressed in red and black: black back bit and black *pallu* covering her torso and pleated to fall below her belly; red blouse and skirt with red floral designs on black. The *oddiyaanam* usually worn over the pallu and skirt is worn underneath the pleats of the pallu. This in no way emphasizes or marks the curve of the waist as is in the case of a character like Sita who is shown having a dainty waistline. It only serves the purpose of holding the dancer's costume and body in proper alignment. The wide pleats of the ends of the pallu which fall over her belly suggest the contours of her bulging waist line. A kaccha (pyjama) is worn underneath the skirt that extends till the ankles. The use of kaccha, as in Jatayu, helps in free and unhindered movement of the legs. The material used for costume is majorly starched cotton which unlike silk used for characters like Sita or court dancers, increases the girth and body volume of the character.

The ornaments like *kaapu*, *thandai*, *haaram*, ear rings, hair ornaments and armlet that are ornaments worn on the wrists and ankles respectively are not of delicate or intricate design nor are they set with stones as in the case of Sita or other aristocratic characters. The traditional *adukkumala* that covers the area from throat to chest, used by traditional Kathakali artists is also worn by her. This perhaps adds to the dramatic element of such characters. On the whole, the workmanship of the jewels used for Surpanakha is made to reflect the primitiveness of the society she lives in.

Movement analysis

Jatayu majorly uses garuda mandala, garuda hasta and arala hasta (used to show wings). Some of the other positions and movements often used here are motita mandala, ayata, sama, prerita, karthari uthplavana, kripalaga-uthplavana, kuttana and kripalaga-kunchitabhramari. Several of the adavus or intermediary positions that pass through different levels, pictures the character as being constantly on the move and illustrates the avian mobile nature of the bird. This is well demonstrated in, for example, the third repetition of the line ‘Tham neela jeemootha....’ In this phrase, Jatayu starts with sama-chalanam, then executes a kripalaga uthplavana jumping to a level above his height and then lands on a front bent knee motitam at the floor level. He again rises to samam to repeat the same phrase accompanied by a synchronous flapping of the wings. The movements of Jatayu are choreographed such that the adavus give scope for expansive placement of the arms and legs to convey the gigantic hugeness of its body and elongated wingspan of the bird which has an outstretched reach. The photo above illustrates one such position. The bird’s movements are choreographed in such a way as to emphasise the turn and flex of the body when stationary and flapping of wings when in flight (second repetition of ‘Tham neela’ and fourth repetition of ‘Tham neela’). The power and strength of sustained motion executed by incessant flapping of its wings in tautly held natyarambham with an erect torso convey a sense of marked majesty in portraying the mythical bird. Preening of its feathers is a typical action of birds. This action is rendered using dhuta shira with prakampita greeva and avalokita drishti.

The other features of this scene are the sections depicting the circular flight trajectory of

the eagle across the sky (stage). It is the character distinct of any bird of prey to encircle the sky. For example, the entire phase of third to fifth ‘Tham neela’ tries to show how the eagle propels itself forward by a constant flinging and flapping of its wings at fluctuating levels of flight. It stops at the centre stage to look out for its prey (with a jerky shira, greeva and drishti) and then continues its flight before landing on the ground in a full garuda mandala (‘prativyaam’). It again takes to flight in the same circular trajectory (seventh ‘Tham neela’) but in an usi with arms in natyarambham showing the fine glide of the eagle. Considering the fact that the depiction of actions and movement of eagle on a stage requires a fair amount of variety, the element of natyadharmi, and the importance given to stylization becomes conspicuous in the depiction of a natural movement pattern of a bird

Let us have a look at the first jati of Surpanakha’s entry. The intonation is provided with emphasis on the first syllable of every alternative word – **thakkudu** dikkudu **dirra** kitta **thakkun** tari **tongita** nangita. The repetition of same character in every sollu/ word place stress on the *kulukki nadai* in chaturashra that is typical of the Kalakshetra school. But here, the stress matters more as it reveals the pounding giant strides of Surpanakha. The torso and arms simultaneously turning right then left emphasizes the nadai. The next line in the jati “tonkita kitakita tonkita takatari kitataka...” is like a torrent of ‘takatakatakataka....’ which creates a vivid image of quick flurry of steps. This contrasts the medium paced thumping mode made at the entry. After a scurried pace diagonally across the stage, Surpanakha stops at left upper stage to position herself with uplifted dola hands. The impression created here is that of the character, a *nishachari*, running amok on the forest floor who then perches

on a rock or tree of considerable height to get a better vantage point to look around her. Her alokita drishti with wide open eyes moving along with frequent jerky moves of the shiras mimics the moves and looks of nocturnal birds like owl or a day scavenger like eagle or vulture which swoops down and glides up before perching itself on a tree with momentarily upraised wings similar to Surpanakha's arms. These moves are interesting and bring a characteristic (identical) feel of a wandering nishachari. This is again followed by a chalana followed by a vegini- a swoop and perch again back and forth to the left upper stage. From there, she takes a wide bhramari with widely placed legs and runs to come to the down-centre stage before executing a theermanam. The angabhramari that is a swirl down from the vantage point where she is perched is unlike the well measured and slickly executed ekapada bhramari of the panchasaras or the kripalaga- kunchita bhramari of Jatayu. Though it is done with control and finesse, it lacks the smoothness which is evident in the other two cases. This is done towards making a rough transit.

A verse follows this theermanam introducing Surpanakha. Hastas like shakatam and mushti are majorly used. Shakatam is used to depict the rakshasa nature of Surpanakha and mushti, her mighty power. To the second line ending in "...aajagaama yaaadrchaya", she is shown with mushti hasta in natyaramba giving the picture of a rakshasi approaching and ready for a fight. The whole sequence shows her basically moving about in the forest looking for a hunt and prepared to pounce on her prey any moment. Another theermanam follows this verse. This typically shows her preparedness or readiness before heading for a fight. The adavus do not have rounded or curved placement of arms but a straight

push or throw emphasizing the power and vigour without grace. Some of the important moves are- both palms held tight on one another; sarukkal adavu with thrust on the push of ardhachandra hands to the sides and the sharp gliding feet; throw of alapadma to sides and forward; walk with extended mushti hands and pounding chalana. The next line of the verse is the last line of her introduction scene. From the attacking mood she exhibits in the theermanam, she again resorts to running and prowling and perching aloft looking for a prey. In the process, she takes a back and forth diagonally across the stage. Finally, there is a repeat of the first sequence of entry with the jathi 'takkudu dikkudu...'. Her exit is interesting as she takes four bhramaris to disappear through the stage right to off stage. It is again four anga bhramaris done continuously to create a picture of whirling down from a height and swooshing past in a jiffy.

Floor patterns

The floor pattern of movement across the stage shows the circular path of flight trajectory of the eagle, Jatayu (fig:1) and diagonal crossings of a nishachari, Surpanakha (Fig:2&3). The choreographic pattern across stage are seen typical of the characters represented.

Tam neela after theermanam

Fig-1

Fig-2

Fig-3

Conclusion

Rukmini Devi, who always vouched for idealized portrayal of characteristics of gods and goddesses in solo items, found a wider canvas for her 'spiritualising' through the dance-dramas. The paper has thrown light on how newer dimensions with regard to stage aesthetics, costuming of characters, intonation of sollu, character and context-oriented use of nritya and angika abhinaya have broadened the scope of choreography in her dance dramas. The paper situates her dance-dramas within the context of nationalism of the pre-independence times that entailed propagating cultural consciousness and collective belonging towards 'restoring' India's glory. Though this perspective further reinstates

her position within the post-colonial critique of the period of nationalism, the analysis of technique undertaken here substantiates that she provides researchers with newer grounds to study her choreographies as being precursors to sowing elements of modernism in dance which seemed to be however blanketed by her continued portrayal as a nationalist.

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